

Music diversity and circulation: Novel data collection methods and indicators

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6465135

Daniel Antal, CFA, Reprex & University of Amsterdam
Scanga, Cateriana, PhD, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
Molina, Andrés GJ, PhD, Reprex

2022-04-16

Abstract

In the last decade, the evidence-based policy movement gained significant traction in Europe as well as globally. Its focus has been to increase the rigour of the evidence generated, to improve the credibility and understandability of evidence created for policy purposes. As evidence-based policies often rely on scientific evidence, the evidence-based policy movement went hand in hand with the efforts to increase the transparency and reproducibility of scientific research (See: (Munafò et al. 2017) and in an EU context (J 2015; Commission et al. 2020; European Commission and Directorate-General for Research and Innovation 2020).)

Our Report on Music Diversity and Circulation in Europe, and its supporting document, Music diversity and circulation: Novel data collection methods and indicators will follow the Open Policy Analysis Guidelines and the best practices of the European Union's Knowledge For Policy and the European Open Science Cloud portal.

The aim of this document is to *share an open report that includes clear accounts of all methodological procedures, data, and assumptions*. Best practice: All project components are organized in a selfcontained folder using a Standard File Structure (SFS), and a readme file is included. We place all files with SFS on the European open science repository Zenodo on zenodo.org/communities/music_observatory/.

Subjects: Reproducible research; Cultural diversity policies; Music industry Recommender systems (Information filtering)

Commission, European, Directorate-General for Research, Innovation, L Baker, I Cristea, T Errington, K Jaško, et al. 2020. *Reproducibility of Scientific Results in the EU : Scoping Report*. Edited by W Lusoli. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/doi/10.2777/341654>.

European Commission, and Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. 2020. *Progress on Open Science Towards a Shared Research Knowledge System. Final Report of the Open Science Policy Platform*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/00139>.

J, Wilson. 2015. *Evidence-Based Policy Making in the European Commission*. Edited by Elisabeth Lannoo. CIC Report 7440. Oslo (Norway): CICERO Centre for International Climate; Environmental Research. <http://www.cicero.uio.no/en/posts/news/report-from-science-to-policy-how-to-improve-the-dialogue/>.

Munafò, Marcus R., Brian A. Nosek, Dorothy V. M. Bishop, Katherine S. Button, Christopher D. Chambers, Nathalie Percie du Sert, Uri Simonsohn, Eric-Jan Wagenmakers, Jennifer J. Ware, and John P. A. Ioannidis. 2017. "A Manifesto for Reproducible Science." *Nature Human Behaviour* 1 (1): 0021. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-016-0021>.